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The social housing in the 1920'ies: the garden city concept

Introduction

A strong anti-urban feeling appears at the end of the 19th century as a reaction against the chaotic developments of the city mainly due to industrialisation in and around the city and the unhealthy and undesirable presence of workers in their proximity. The search for a better living environment reflects this anti-urban reaction and finds an alternative in the autonomous, green settlement developed without any relation to the city: this can be seen as the historical origin of the development of the garden city concept that will have its time of glory in Belgium just after the First World War. (SMETS, 1977: pp. 68-77.)

The concept of garden city is promoted by the *Garden City Association* founded in 1899 by the progressive Sir E. Howard as a remedy against an uncontrolled urban growth and the disintegration of social bonds. In his book *Tomorrow: A Peaceful Path to Real Reform*, he proposes to create economically autonomous communities in green entities following the cooperative ideals of production of John Ruskin's and William Morris' *Arts and Crafts* (ill. 1). The *Garden City Association* permitted to the young R. Unwin, in association with B. Parker, to concrete these new social convictions in the garden city of Letchworth in 1904 and Hampstead in 1905. In the book he published in 1909 under the title *Town Planning in Practice. An introduction to the art of designing cities and suburbs*, Unwin insists on an urbanism based on the cooperative ideals and the active participation of the inhabitants in order to achieve a social integration thanks to the common use of collective equipment (HOWARD, 1970: p. 51).

In its social attainments, the garden city has to be considered as a radical rupture with the repressive and paternalist intentions of the social housing theories of the 19th century. It thus represents a modern and particularly progressive social approach to the needs of social housing inhabitants in terms of hygiene and comfort thanks to a healthy, organised environment with common amenities.

The historical evolution of the garden city concept in Belgium

The concept of the garden city was already present in Belgium before the First World War. Belgian architects and urban planners played an active role during the 7^e *Congrès international d'architectes* (London, 1906), the *Town-Planning Conference* (London, 1910) and the *Premier congrès international et exposition comparée des villes* (Ghent, 1913) where a progressive impulse was given to the renewal of urban concepts expressing the transition from the bourgeois aesthetic urban concept of the 19th to the more social preoccupations present at the beginning of the 20th century, prefiguring the Modern Movement. (VANDENBREEDEN & VANLAETHEM, 1996: pp. 119-121.)

Initially however, the garden city concept will not be adopted in Belgium as solution to ameliorate the conditions of workers housing. It was associated with a suburban quarter of villas following the principles of the Frenchman G. Benoit-Levy published in 1904 under the title *La Cité-Jardin*. M. Benoit-Levy studied the outstanding garden cities of Letchworth, Port Sunlight and Bournville on a trip to Britain, but completely missed the social intentions of those in his description, focusing instead on the idyllic, romantic look of nice little cottages in a green area (BENOIT-LEVY, 1904: pp. 107-108.). This misunderstanding is at the origin of the foundation of the *Association des Cités-jardins en Belgique*, inspired by the *Association des Cités-jardins françaises* under the direction of the same G. Benoit-Levy, which promoted the construction of individual villas in suburban green areas without no attempts at social housing. Because this *Association* didn't build anything it was dissolved after one year and replaced by the *Société des Nouveaux Quartiers Jardins* founded in Brussels in 1906. Its aim was to allow the middle class to attain ownership, and to offer proper common accommodations to the inhabitants with individualised houses. (SMETS, 1977: pp. 78-80.)

The distinction between the garden city concept for bourgeois or middle class customers represented by the *Société des Nouveaux Quartiers Jardins* and neighbourhoods for the working class in open areas close to their factories existed until the foundation of the industrial village of Winterslag ON the garden city concept.

The first (of 3) industrial village of Winterslag, built for the Limburg coalmines by Adrien Blomme in 1912, is the only garden city realized in Belgium before the First World War. A large avenue with an important amount of common amenities, two schools, a church and a theatre, crosses the neighbourhood and leads from the industrial zone to a park. A loop road encircles the settlement in order to facilitate security control in case of demonstration, and some artificially sinuous roads furrow the settlement. Groups of cottage-like dwellings for workers as well as for employees are built for 2, 4 or more families and have each a small garden. Even if this first realisation appears as a clumsy attempt to marry the advantages of living in a green and healthy environment outside the city with community intentions, it still is an industrial village with paternalist and security intentions. It cannot be said that the garden city social ideals as expressed by Raymond Unwin are adopted in Winterslag. (WILLEMSEN, 1991) (HEYDEN & LOECKX, 1991)

Paradoxically, the First World War catalyzed the emancipation of the garden city concept in Belgium. Massive destructions (about 120.000 dwellings destroyed during the war) are the argument for the organisation of several reconstruction associations in foreign countries where Belgian architects and urban planners lived in exile (SMETS, 1977: pp. 90-92): the *Belgium Town Planning Committee* in London, the *Comité Néerland-Belge d'Art Civique* in Amsterdam, the committee *Pour la reconstruction des villes* in Switzerland, the *Commission d'étude franco-belge*, a special commission of the *American Society of Landscape architects* and the Danish *Akademisk architect forening*. An important event was the *Reconstruction Conference* organised in London in 1915 by the *International Garden Cities and Town Planning Association* (founded in 1899 by E. Howard) under the direction of the garden city specialist, the architect Raymond Unwin. Many Belgian politicians, urbanists and architects like J.-J. Eggericx, Th. Clément and R. Verwilghen participated in this conference that adopted a.o. the principle of the garden city for the reconstruction to come. The *Comité Néerland-Belge d'Art Civique* unites Dutch personalities like H.P. Berlage and J.Th. Cuypers and Belgian architects like H. Hoste, L. Van der Swaelmen and the progressive utopian "mundialist" P. Otlet. They were confronted with the progressive ideas of social housing politics in The Netherlands and influenced by the "brick expressionism" of the *School of Amsterdam* and early concrete modernism (VANDEN-BREEDEN & VANLAETHEM, 1996: p. 117). In this context, the landscape architect L. Van der Swaelmen published his *Préliminaires d'Art Civique* in which he presents a socio-biological approach to urbanism

based on a machinist interpretation of the industrial society. In opposition to Unwin, he sees industrialisation as a positive opportunity to more equity and democracy for the working class (SMETS, 1977: pp. 92-94). As he pleads for a rational and functional approach to urbanism, Van der Swaelmen's principles can be considered as an important premise to the *Charte d'Athènes*. He will participate in the elaboration of the most interesting garden cities in Belgium after the First World War.

The Belgian garden cities

Introduction

Unfortunately, after the war, the new generation of primarily young architects and planners influenced by the latest modern developments were little involved in the reconstruction process. The government preferred to focus on temporary dwellings like wooden barracks. Nevertheless, under the impulse of R. Verwilghen, first director of the *Service des Constructions des Régions Dévastées*, some small social garden cities in traditional style were built in Flanders (SMETS, 1977: pp. 98-105): Comines (1920, J.-J. Eggericx), *Batavia* (Roeselare, 1920, R. Verwilghen, A. Pompe and F. Bodson), *Kalfvaart* (Ypres, 1921, R. Acke), *Ligy* (Ypres, 1922, R. Verwilghen).

However, the modernist architects had their opportunity to express their ideals in social housing. In 1919, a new law, inspired by the socialists, extended state intervention in housing to avoid wild real estate speculation; this in turn led to the founding of the *Société Nationale des Habitations à Bon Marché*. The aim of the *SNHBM* was to build cheap dwellings, thanks to the creation of local cooperatives, in order to allow the working class and the middle class to rent or to buy a decent property. The same year, R. Verwilghen, F. Bodson, L. Van der Swaelmen, E. Van Averbek, J. De Ligne, H. Hoste, De Bruyne, de Ridder, Thirion, Patris and Van de Voorde found the *Société des Urbanistes Belges* with solid modernist principles expressed in their official revue *La Cité* (1919-1935). The *S.U.B.* became the *Société des Urbanistes et Architectes Modernistes* in 1923 (dismantled in 1970) and its ranks grew to include famous members like V. Bourgeois, J.-F. Hoeben and P. Rubbers. The first conference of the *SNHBM* in 1920 established the urban model of the garden city with important social, hygienic and economical bases. Therefore, a *Comptoir National des Matériaux* was created in 1921 in order to promote and to experiment the use of new materials and construction techniques.

In its early years, the *SNHBM* furnished 25% of the entire production of dwellings; and had built about 55.000 dwellings by 1934.

Standardisation and industrialisation are now key notions for the construction of social housing, al-

though formally, only some of the dwellings adopted the modernist aesthetic, while others remained traditional cottage-like dwellings.

Case studies

Among the many garden cities built in the 1920's, let us only mention the most significant ones in order to show their importance in the field of urban development.

1. *Klein Rusland*

This large industrial village built in Zelzate by H. Hoste in 1921-23 along the industrially important channel Ghent-Terneuzen must be considered as the first modernist application of the garden city concept in Belgium. The village was an initiative of the SNHBM and 4 important local industrialists. Originally, some of the dwellings were built in a traditional way with brick bearing walls, others with the German "Non-plus" construction system: load bearing walls in cinder concrete, cast in place with reusable wooden formwork one storey high. The use of an industrialised construction technique permits the emergence of a new aesthetic. Indeed, the architect, inspired by H.P. Berlage and *De Stijl*, adopts here sober "cubist" architecture with flat roofs. Functional intentions of economy and not formal means prevail in this realisation. (SMETS, 1977: pp. 114, 125-127)

L. Van der Swaelmen designed the urban plan (ill. 2). His intention was to consider *Klein Rusland* as the starting point of an industrial linear city that was never realised. The central avenue that crosses the neighbourhood was meant to be the axis of this much larger project. The urban divisions and subdivisions follow an orthogonal concept. But each of the streets, blocks, corners and plots is deliberately treated in a different way in order to create a sequence of constantly varying views (VANDENBREEDEN & VAN LAETHEM, 1996: pp. 125-126). The various groups of houses are symmetrically denticulated with this intention; it stresses the global "cubist" impression. The central square is dominated by A house for unmarried men; it's the only collective dwelling with amenities to serve the inhabitants.

2. *Cité Moderne*

The young and progressive V. Bourgeois is certainly one of the outstanding protagonists of the Modern Movement in Belgium. Together with his brother P. Bourgeois, he founded the weekly revue *7 Arts* (1922-1928), a strong progressive, modernist periodical, with links to both the Belgian and international artistic avant-garde. (BOURGEOIS, 1952: pp. 12-17)

This garden city was constructed in the Brussels suburbs (Berchem-Saint-Agathe) between 1922-

1925. This well-known chef d'oeuvre of the *International Style* must be seen as the manifesto of Belgian modernism. G. Rens, V. Bourgeois and his brother P. Bourgeois founded a social cooperative especially for the occasion. The initial project aimed at 500 dwellings together with collective facilities such as a school, a public bathhouse, a meeting hall, a library and shops. Only 274 dwellings and a few shops were built. Bourgeois designed 15 types of minimal houses and apartments of varying size and configuration. After several study trips to France, The Netherlands and especially to Merzeburg in Germany, they decided to utilize the simple, inexpensive "Non-plus" system (VANDENBREEDEN & VAN LAETHEM, 1996: pp. 125, 130-131). This method allowed construction of an average dwelling in only 12 days and reduced the overall budget by 14%.

Unlike *Klein Rusland*, solar orientation is taken into account by V. Bourgeois, who designed the urban plan in collaboration with L. Van der Swaelmen. He organizes groups of dwellings in "cubist" volumes by which he articulated squares, crossings and closed perspectives. The denticulated central avenue has the same intention of creating broken perspectives as in *Klein Rusland* and has also the effect of slowing down traffic. The main square, *Place des Coopérateurs*, has a monumental centrality by the disposition of the surrounding saw-tooth houses and the higher denticulate corner building with stores signifying the hierarchical importance of the square (ill. 3). This building is decorated with abstract *De Stijl*-like stained glass designed by P.-L. Flouquet. (PUTTEMANS, 1974: pp. 123, 136-137)

Victor Bourgeois will be internationally known as a modernist architect upon completion of this project. In 1927, he will be one of the architects invited to build a house at the *Weissenhofsiedlung* in Stuttgart. As vice-president of the C.I.A.M., he will also organize the third C.I.A.M. in Brussels in 1930 on the matter of high-rise building. He will participate to the large-scale urban projects for *Le Nouveau Bruxelles*, adopting the principles of the radical urban principles of Le Corbusier. (VAN LOO, 1994: pp. 197-203)

3. *Floréal* and *Le Logis*

These two joint garden cities are built in the green suburb of Watermael-Boitsfort, in the south-east of Brussels, under the direction of architect J.-J. Eggericx and landscape architect L. Van der Swaelmen with the collaboration of R. Moenaert and L. François between 1921-1930 (PUTTEMANS, 1974: pp. 124-126). Formally, the 1600 dwellings with a capacity of about 6000 inhabitants testify of a much more traditionalist cottage-like design. The uneven topography does not permit an orthogonal

organisation of the urban plan with a correct orientation and procures a global picturesque impression (ill. 4). Main avenues, as straight as possible in this difficult relief, are serving furrowed streets with smaller subdivisions like squares of various shapes. Small inner paths testify of the intention to separate the car traffic network from a more private pedestrian set of connections. A 9-storey building on a horseshoe shape square creates the link between the two garden cities. This was the highest apartment building of Brussels and the first time that a high apartment building was integrated into a garden city concept (VANDENBREEDEN & VAN LAETHEM, 1996: pp. 127-129). Stores are located on the street level of that building and the low horseshoe shape buildings around. With its strong urban imprint, the building has an evident symbolic significance as rallying element for the inhabitants and can be seen as a kind of meeting centre. (SMETS, 1977: pp. 111-114, 128-131)

This realisation can be quoted for its exemplary social integration till 1926, when the social housing cooperative was dismantled. From then on already, a gentrification of the neighbourhood took place.

4. Kapelleveld

This garden city has been built in Woluwe-Saint-Lambert, in the periphery of Brussels, by the architects A. Pompe, H. Hoste, J.-F. Hoeben, P. Rubbers on the urban plan of L. Van der Swaelmen between 1923-1926. The cubist dwellings built by H. Hoste are in contrast with the more conventional ones built by the other architects. As the social housing cooperative of *Kapelleveld* was aimed AT intellectual workers, a studio is added in the plan between the living room and the kitchen and a bathroom, a luxury for that period, serves the bedrooms (VANDEN-BREEDEN & VAN LAETHEM, 1996: pp. 125-126, 132-133).

All the 225 dwellings are built with the "Celtic" concrete construction system. (VANDAMME, 1998: pp. 100-104, 207-223)

Kapelleveld consists of a flat area and a slope area. The urban plan of the flat area is much simpler and readable than the former analysed garden cities. Three main avenues diverge from an important cross-road; perpendicular streets with grouped dwellings are joining the avenues. A circular "square" breaks the uniformity of each perpendicular intersection. The slope area is laid out with sinuous roads, but maintains the same circular "squares" found in the flats. Amenities for sports are found at the slope limit of the garden city. The original project of H. Hoste aimed to build four apartment towers of four levels situated as transition elements between the residential area and the zone for sport, but these were never executed. (SMETS, 1977: pp. 126, 138-139)

5. La Roue/Het Rad

This garden city built in the periphery of Brussels between 1921-1922 is not that relevant for its urban concept but is significant for the importance of the experimental approach of the social housing construction technology at this time. (VANDENBREEDEN & VANLAETHEM, 1996: pp. 124-125)

The social building cooperative association of Anderlecht, a suburb of Brussels, called *Le Foyer Anderlechtois* and the *Comptoir National des Matériaux* decided to build an experimental garden city of 67 dwellings divided in 20 blocks. The project was under the direction of the modernist architect J.-J. Eggericx with the collaboration of the architects Pompe, Meckmans, Jonghers and Voets. It was decided to test 21 known concrete construction techniques to have an objective and rational appreciation of their capacity, cost, comfort and durability. The majority of the known concrete construction techniques in Europe are mentioned below; they are divided in four categories. The different experimental techniques used for the construction of the garden city *La Roue/Het Rad* are present among these categories (cf. Annexe 1, VANDAMME, 1998: pp. 60-66, 85-201).

City social housing concept

A secondary parallel to the development of the garden city concept was the interweaving of new social housing into the existing urban tissue. The same concerns of hygiene and comfort were adopted for this urban social housing. Collective amenities were also considered to be necessary to favour community bonds; therefore housing blocks were constructed around a large inner court holding these amenities, although most unfortunately, resumed to a washhouse. The housing blocks were restricted to 3 or 4 levels, essentially for security reasons and to avoid the expensive construction of elevators. When it was established that the common amenities were not used as planned, the typology of the blocks regressed to more traditional ranged joint housing blocks in the existing street structure.

The end of the garden city concept

At the end of the 1920's, modernist architects and town planners broke with the ideal of the garden city because of financial restrictions and lack of interest of the authorities due to the reinstatement of a conservative government after 1926. The new government instituted a policy preferring the construction of individual housing and private ownership, more specifically in rural or suburban areas, through the creation by law in 1935 of the *Société Nationale de la Petite Propriété Terrienne*, an initiative of the Catholic minister Moyersoën. This radi-

cal change can also be explained by the fear of some of creating a concentration of the leftist working class in large-scale social housing entities. People spoke at that time of the danger of "a red belt" around Brussels".

At the same time, the urban ideas of high-rise buildings defended by Le Corbusier in his *Ville Radieuse* and his *Plan Voisin* were expounded during the third *Congrès Internationale d'Architecture Moderne* (C.I.A.M.) in Brussels in 1930 (VANDENBREEDEN & VAN LAETHEM, 1996: pp. 202-204). Most of the modernist architects and town planners proceeded to abandon the garden city concept to pursue research on radical urban large-scale projects with high-rise buildings that would offer artistically beautiful utopian projects. (VAN LOO, 1994: pp. 197-202): *Le Nouveau Bruxelles* by V. Bourgeois (1930), *Projet de cité administrative* by S. Jasinski (1930) (ill. 5), linear city project by G. Herbosch (1933), linear city project by R. Braem (1934), project for the extension of the left bank of Antwerp by Le Corbusier, H. Hoste and Locquet (1933), ¼ (VANDENBREEDEN & VAN LAETHEM, 1996: pp. 206-209)

The art school of "La Cambre", founded in 1926 by Henry Van de Velde, became an essential tool for the diffusion of modernist ideas in the fields of urban planning, architecture and arts as most of the protagonists of the Modern Movement in Belgium took up teaching posts there.

II. The social housing in the 1950's-1960's: high-rise ensembles

Introduction

The situation after the Second World War was completely different in that there was far less housing destroyed than in the First World War, or had occurred in the surrounding nations, which meant that there was not an acute housing shortage. Therefore, from the moment the economy took off, the government instead decided to promote a general modernization of public services and infrastructure. Government buildings, offices, banks, schools, sports and cultural centres arose while an ambitious infrastructure policy started with the construction of the national airport, the modernization and extension of the commercial harbour of Antwerp, and an unbounded net of highways (BEKAERT, 1996: pp. 7-13). The idea was to enhance through this large-scale investment a completely liberalized free market economy, a unique situation in post-war Europe. In regard to housing, the government continued the 1930's policy of private ownership of individual houses on small privately owned lots. The pre-war Moyersoen-law of 1935 was implanted by the 1948

De Taeye-law on the construction of privately owned low cost houses; once again a Catholic initiative defending the individual family against every form of exaggerated collectivism. By 1954, 100.000 subsidized dwellings were already built on this model. This led to a predominance, to this day, of the construction of individual houses, even in the sector of public housing. In the urban context, the debate about high-rise building is now fully opened (BEKAERT & STRAUVEN, 1971: pp. 63-67).

The evolution of the high-rise social housing concept

In 1949 the socialist minister and architect F. Brunfaut, reintroduced a policy of high-density collective housing. High-rise buildings and collective facilities testify to a post-war modern image of social housing expressing a form of pragmatic, planified socialism, reflecting the socio-political and urban principles of the *Charte d'Athènes* are. The formal influence of Le Corbusier was adopted in some of the most significant examples of social ensembles and adapted to the Belgian situation. (PUTTEMANS, 1974: pp. 156-242)

During the 1950's-1960's, the availability of social housing explodes. At the same time, the notion of minimal comfort is redefined: an individual bathroom, an equipped kitchen, an automatic refuse-bin and even sometimes a inner phone are the new norms. Green spaces and collective amenities such as schools, medical, sport and cultural centres, shops etc. are always present in the design of the projects as the symbols of community, modern life and progress. But large open spaces and public facilities were not always completed as initially designed due the financial problems high idealistic aspirations of the projects; spatial coherence and urban character are missing in many cases because of the elimination of the collective amenities. A further lack of interest and maintenance makes these ensembles problematic nowadays.

Among the most relevant examples, one can mention the dwellings designed and built by Ch. Van Nueten in a popular neighbourhood of Brussels for the *Foyer Bruxellois* (social housing cooperative of Brussels) in 1950, first application of the Brunfaut-law in the very centre of a city; the completed *Champ des Manoeuvres (Droixhe)* ensemble built by the "Groupe EGAU" (Ch. Carlier, H. Lhoest and J. Mozin) in Liège between 1951-1961; the *Kiel* ensemble built by R. Braem, R. Maes and V. Maeremans in Antwerp between 1951-1958; the idealistic *Cité modèle* built by R. Braem, V. Coolens, J. Van Doosselaere, R. Panis, "Groupe L'Equerre" and "Structures" in the suburb of Brussels between 1956-1969. (BEKAERT, 1996: pp. 22-25, 40-46)

Case studies

Kiel (1951-1958)

Kiel is a neighbourhood in the periphery of Antwerp where 3 waves of social housing construction exhibit in a dense area the evolution of the politics of social architecture Belgium from the turn of the century. The third wave was conceived by R. Braem in the spirit of the C.I.A.M. and encouraged by the Brunfaut-law of 1949.

Braem, born in 1910, can be considered as one of the most important protagonists of modern urban and architectural concepts after the Second World War. Strongly left orientated, he defends the idea of architecture as a tool to achieve a better world, "revolution by architecture", and militates for an ordained urban planning against the chaotic evolution of the built environment. He is also the founder of the avant-garde revue "Bouwen en Wonen" in 1952; his writings are still examples of revolutionary engaged principles for a new ordained society. (BRAEM, 1952-1962: *Bouwen en Wonen*.)

The architect worked on the project in collaboration with V. Maeremans and R. Maes from 1947. The project consists of 3 blocks of 12 levels and 6 blocks of 8 stores in zigzag formation with a capacity of 694 apartments, 5 shops and a central heating plant. A cluster with a home for the elderly was built a bit later and gives a specific definition to the big empty space between the buildings. The 4 different types of apartments and duplexes are located along an outside gallery slightly lower than the entrance offering more light and view without the incommodities of curious neighbours. (STRAUVEN, 1985: pp. 60-66) (BEKAERT & Strauven, 1971: pp. 64-66.)

The 3 higher blocks are located around a huge square (ill. 6). Braem projected a socio-cultural centre but it was considered too ambitious and was finally reduced to a small meeting building. The blocks are oriented southeast and southwest in order to maximize sun exposure. All the blocks are built on pilotis as a symbol of the collectivisation of the ground and to offer a horizon to the inhabitants.

Even if the socio-cultural centre and the urban furniture that the architects conceived were never realized, Braem considers this ensemble as his first exemplary attainment of the C.I.A.M. ideals. The concept preaches freedom, space, green and light. The V-shape of the blocks guarantees an open view to the inhabitants without endangering their privacy. Braem considers an open view to the horizon as a "human right" (BRAEM, 1987: 99). The stairs and the elevators are situated in the hinge of the V shaped building. This characteristic and the transparency of technical services are participating in the ornamentation of the architecture and procure a kind of tectonic legibility of the function of the building.

The monumental and transparent central plant with a huge chimney enhances the awareness of community; it can also be seen as a symbol of comfort attainment.

Two anecdotes about the Kiel are relevant for the misunderstood project of this revolutionary approach and the personal modernity ideals applied by Braem in this project.

-During the construction, the conservative journal "La Libre Belgique" expressed its indignation that the authorities were subsidizing buildings with empty street levels! (PUTTEMANS, 1974: p. 174). -Le Corbusier, in whose office Braem worked between 1935-1937 CRITIQUED the plan of the apartments; they were too large and not profound enough in his eyes. Braem retorted that Antwerp does not benefit of that much sun as in Marseille and that sun exposure has to be considered as a priority in this case. (STRAUVEN, 1985: pp. 65-66)

Champ des Manoeuvres (Droixhe) (1951-1961)

The competition organized by the housing cooperative *La Maison Liégeoise* in 1950 for the construction of an important social ensemble on the river Meuse was won by Ch. Carlier, H. Lhoest and J. Mozin united in the "Groupe EGAU" (PUTTE-MANS, 1974: p. 218). The urban principle of rationalisation of space was the basis of their approach: the ensemble is divided into neighbourhood units of 2000 dwellings and subdivided into residential units of 500 dwellings. Separation of functions, hygiene, orientation, security and comfort are articulated in the elaboration of the project. At the moment, the ensemble has 1840 dwellings divided into 18 residential units with a total capacity of more than 7000 inhabitants. A circle made by 12-storey buildings creates a protective belt around the public square and the park where the collective amenities are located (ill. 7). *Champ des Manoeuvres* is probably the only large-scale social ensemble in Belgium completed with all its projected equipment (BEKAERT 1996: p. 25.). A church, schools, crèche, libraries, medical centre, cultural centre, shops, police station, parks, public squares and parking providing this social ensemble with an autonomous village atmosphere. In order to break with the monotony of the double range of the highest blocks, some lower buildings of 4 levels have been built in between them to provide appropriate dwellings for large families. (CRAPPE, 1962: pp. 119-143.)

The buildings are embellished by abstract geometry art conceived by local artists such as J. Rets, J. Delahau, P. Bury and G. Collignon. (BOSMANT, 1962: pp. 147-150.)

The ensemble was completed by other buildings in a later construction phase till 1970 and is actually known as *Droixhe*.

Even if nowadays *Droixhe* is considered as a difficult quarter, its undeniable architectural and urban qualities are making from it one of the most significant and achieved examples of large-scale high-rise social housing in Belgium.

Cité Modèle/Modelwijk (1956-1969)

This project was decided by the government to illustrate the advanced policy in social housing in Belgium for the Universal Exhibition of 1958 ("Expo 58"). Braem had to collaborate with V. Coolens, J. Van Dooselaere, R. Panis, the "Groupe Equerre" and the "Groupe Structures" to answer to the difficult political and linguistic equilibrium of a state commission. (BEKAERT, 1996: pp. 40-48) The strongly idealist and leftist architect wanted to build a ordained and clear orthogonal urban plan (ill.8), in contrast with "the chaos of the streets and the incoherent buildings of the next environment" (BRAEM, 1960: p. 16.), with multi-level buildings and public facilities like school, library, cultural centre and church to educate the people to a better and more interesting life (PUTTEMANS, 1974: pp. 222-225). Finally, 942 dwellings in 12 high-rise buildings of different types were built. Unfortunately, as in most cases, most of the public amenities were not built due to financial problems. (STRAUVEN, 1985: pp. 75-78.)

The project of the *Cité Modèle* was the first heavy industrialized wharf of prefabrication building in Belgium, utilizing the French Barets and Cauvet systems (NOVGORODSKY, 1966: pp. 2-18.).

The *Cité modèle* is built on a sloped triangular site of 17 hectares.

The urban concept reflects the idealistic ambitions of Braem. A very long block of 5 stores closes the ensemble from the main street on the side of the expo. The intention of Braem is to protect the inhabitants of the *Cité* from the baneful influence of the expo. A large monumental stair leads the pedestrian from this street side to a small covered open square from which the orthogonal distribution through the ensemble begins (ill. 9). From there, the pedestrian access walks under a building on pilotis to the main square where most of the collective amenities are located: pub, restaurant, cultural centre and social centre. A double flight of stairs leads from this main square to the greenspace and children's areas. Braem voluntarily separates pedestrian and car traffic. The interior of the ensemble, traversed by paths for pedestrians and bicycles, benefits from a beautiful verdure. Cars access to the parkings of the *Cité modèle* by 5 roads. The design of the 2 networks is orthogonal and well ordered, permitting a clear reading and a rapid and easy distribution of the social ensemble. (BRAEM, 1958: pp. 267-289.)

Braem utilizes the technical characteristics of the heavy industrialized prefabrication systems in the architectural expression of his projects. It can be said that his architecture is concerned by a human social ideal translated by a strong and temperate constructive truth.

Conclusion

The development of social housing concepts at the turn of the 19th and 20th century is a decisive step in the evolution of more socially linked and rational urban planning. It generates a rich debate of ideas and permits the emergence of an ordained and well-thought space organisation with community intentions: the garden city. *Préliminaires d'Art Civique*, written by L. Van der Swaelmen during the First World War, will be the theoretical base for the further development of the urban plan of most of the garden cities during the 1920's; Van der Swaelmen will collaborate with most of the urban design of the garden cities in Belgium. The conditions of the First World War attributes to the Belgian situation a unique platform for experiences - technical, formal and urban, in the field of the garden city, with the latest influences from abroad.

Two facts endanger the heritage values and the integrity of the social intentions of the designers. The partial gentrification of these neighbourhoods is not a vain consequence of their living quality. This fashion movement raises prices and tends to foster the loss of social intentions. Another important problem is the lack of a preconceived intervention plan when restoration becomes necessary. Individual embellishment initiatives are perhaps even worse than the lack of attention. Therefore, the listing of the garden cities as a whole and a uniform maintenance and restoration policy must be adopted in order to respect the formal characteristics of the garden city. Some initiatives in that sense are in study at the moment (FRANCHINI, 1999: pp. 138-167).

The high-rise ensembles of the 1950's-1960's are probably the only examples of organized, orthogonal urban planning in a wild and sometimes chaotic urban development. The ideologically engaged personality of R. Braem, as theorist and practitioner, is undeniable for the progress of the concept of large-scale high-rise social ensembles with a strongly implemented urban idealism adopted from the principles of *La Charte d'Athènes*.

Penury of image and bad social reputation are the main problems of the large-scale high-rise social ensembles at the moment. A denser social life could give a new impulse to them. The completion of the projected collective equipments in an actualised answer to the new needs, but still respectful of the original concept, can offer this amelioration. Further, the listing of these social ensembles should be considered to facilitate a coordinated heritage intervention.

Fig 1 – Ebenezer Howard: diagram of a model garden city, 1898.
Source: "Garden-Cities of Tomorrow", London, 1902.

Fig. 2 – Louis Van der Swaelmen, urban plan of Klein Rusland;
Source: collection Sint-Lukasarchief, Brussels

Fig. 3 – Victor Bourgeois, *Cité moderne*.
Source: collection A.A.M., Brussels.

Fig. 4 – Main architect Jean-Jules Eggerix and urban planner Louis Van der Swaelmen, aerial view of *Le Logis-Floréal*.
Source: Vandenbreenen Jos & Vanlaethem France, «Art deco et modernisme en Belgique. Architecture de l'Entre-deux-guerres», ed. Racine, Brussels, 1996, p. 127.
Picture by Christine Bastin & Jacques Evard.

Fig. 5 – Stanislas Jasinski, project for an administrative city in the historic centre of Brussels.
Source: collection A.A.M., Brussels.

Fig. 6 – Renaat Braem, *Kiel* social housing in Antwerp.
Source: collection A.A.M., Brussels.

Fig. 7 – Groupe EGAU, Charles Charlier, Hyacinthe Lhoest & Jules Mozin: *Droxhe* social housing in Liège.
 Source: Bekaert Geert, "Architecture contemporaine en Belgique", ed. Racine, Brussels, 1995, p. 25.
 Picture by Christine Bastin & Jacques Evrard.

Fig. 8 – Renaat Braem, J. Van Dooselaere, R. Panis, Groupe Equerre & Groupe Structures: *Cité modèle* social housing in Brussel.
 Source: collection A.A.M., Brussels.

Fig. 9 – Renaat Braem, J. Van Dooselaere, R. Panis, Groupe Equerre & Groupe Structures:
Cité modèle social housing in Brussel.
Source: Jean-Marc Basyn

KEYWORDS

social housing, garden-city, large scale high rise ensembles, urban concept, analysis and conservation policy

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